

DETECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF FUNGAL DISEASE ON PLANT LEAVES USING CNN

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ABSTRACT

In this era of modernization, where every aspect of society is growing exponentially, the demand for healthy and nutritious food remains the same. So protecting plants from disease becomes very important.

In a country like India, where farmers are not so well trained and educated to fight against plant diseases, computer vision can play an important role in assisting them.

Using their smartphones they can upload pictures of diseased plant's leaf and get to know about the disease.

In this project, we will look into the details of CNN and its use in Image Processing and how the model was made and trained to attain an accuracy of 93.18%. The model was further implemented through Python's framework FLASK to link it to the website's User Interface. The website was made in Hindi language for the ease of Farmers.

Keywords: Convolution Neural Network, Plant Disease, Python's framework FLASK

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has been a major contributor in the GDP of India, around 70% of people are dependent on agriculture for their source of income. Thus it is important for the growth of the country that the agricultural sector keeps pace with the changing time.

The major hindrance in the growth of the agriculture sector has been the effect of pathogens which has led to various kinds of diseases in plants. According to the Indian Council of Agriculture Research, around 30-35% of crops are destroyed because of pathogens every year.

Crop Loss due to Pathogens

Figure 1: Crop Loss

The diseases have led to the decrease in the quality of the plants by hampering the nutrition value which has further affected the quantity. As a result the economic output of various sectors which are dependent on agriculture, also decreases. Thus it is important to look into this matter very carefully for the sustainable growth of the country.

The farmers in India are mostly uneducated and they hardly understand the English language and the conventional method of examining the plant leaf manually, isn't that fruitful also. Thus, there arises a need of technology and Computer Vision does this job perfectly with the advancement of various methods for image processing, the accuracy and speed both have increased drastically and especially the CNN algorithm which has kept on improving over the time, is the best algorithm for image and video analysis.

There has been number of models already made like "Detection and Classification of leaf disease using Artificial Neural Network" by Malvika Ranjan et al. [1] where they developed a model to detect a plant's illness, with an

accuracy of 80%. Kulkarni et al. [2] in the paper—“ Applying image processing technique to detect plant diseases ” , a method for detecting plant diseases early and accurately using an artificial neural network (ANN). The accuracy was found out to be 91%

Chen et al. [3] In the paper--- “ Using deep transfer learning for image-based plant disease identification ” used VGGNet pre-trained on ImageNet and Inception module and got an accuracy of 91.83%

Rangarajan Aravind, K.; Raja, P. ” [4] Automated disease classification in (Selected) agricultural crops using transfer learning. ” achieved the best accuracy of 97.3%. The above-mentioned models are either still under development or the implemented ones are rarely used in practice in our country. The reason being the implemented models are in English language.

II. METHODOLOGY

The whole process is divided into two major sections. First the preparation of the model and second the implementation of the model.

Model Preparation

The preparation of the model begins with selecting a dataset of adequate size. In this case the dataset consist of 1820 images of 2048*1365 pixels so first we decrease the size of the images to 210*210 pixels and then put each one of them for the feature extraction, where important information is extracted from the image which is further used to train the model and depending upon the cost function, using backpropagation, the weights of neurons are modified in the fully connected layer. The model is trained to identify the plant in four major categories namely Healthy Leaf having no disease, Rusted leaf having rust on a certain portion of the leaf, Scab disease and the last category includes leaf having more than one disease.

Figure 2: Categories of the model

Implementation of website

After the model is trained for every image, the model is linked with the back-end of the website and when the user uploads the image of the plant leaf, it is fed to the model and the output returned from it, is displayed on the user’s screen.

III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

The CNN architecture is shown below in figure 1. The input image is preprocessed, the color format is changed to RGB and the size is decreased to 210*210 pixels.

Figure 3: CNN Architecture

Data Augmentation

As the number of images are less. So to produce a large number of different image patterns, the existing images were augmented by changing the orientation, scaling, contrast and brightness. Augmentation helps in increasing the training dataset and feeding more images to the model. Thus increasing the accuracy of the model.

Feature Extraction

Feature Extraction is the process in which parts of an object in the image are extracted which would help in the identification of the image. The Feature Extraction network consists of a number of Convolution layer and Pooling layer pairs. In the Convolution layer, the input image is convolved with the digital filters whose value is chosen randomly in the beginning and as the training progresses, with the help of Back-propagation, its values are altered accordingly. In the Activation layer, it is decided if a neuron will be fired or not. Here, we used ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) Activation function, if the value in the neuron is negative then it is made zero and only the positively valued neurons are activated. Thus it makes the computation relatively faster. In the Pooling Layer, the number of parameters are decreased and thus the number of computations are also reduced. Max Pooling layer was used in this project. After the convolution process, the filter is slid over the convolved images and on each step, the maximum value is selected and the rest are dropped out. This way the size of the image and computation cost reduces. After performing the Convolution and the Pooling, a certain number of times. We flatten the 2D images in One Dimensional array, which is then connected to the Fully Flattened Layer and act as an input.

Image Classifier

The first layer is connected to every neuron of the flattened layer. The final layer of Fully Connected Layers consists of a sigmoid activation function, which gives the output as the probability of each output category for the given image. The Fully Connected Layers are also used to train the model, the output from the final layer is used to calculate the cost function. The cost function gives us the amount of error that the model is getting while making the predictions. So to decrease the cost function, and increase the accuracy of the model, BackPropagation is done using Adam optimizer which is currently the best optimizer available. After going through the whole dataset multiple times the model is prepared and the best value of accuracy during the preparation decides the overall accuracy of the model.

After the model is prepared, it is connected to the User Interface through the back-end which is written in FLASK.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After training the model for 30 Epochs. The model gained an accuracy of 93.18%.

Figure 4: Model Accuracy

The implemented website is responsive as well. Thus it provides a good experience on mobile.

- On desktop the website looks like

- On the mobile it looks like

Steps to get the result

Step 1- Open the website and click on पौधे के पत्ते की छवि चुने

Step 2- Choose the image of the plant leaf

Step-3 Click on जानकारी प्राप्त करे

Result

V. CONCLUSION

Through this paper I have tried to bring the agriculture sector close to technology and made the user interface convenient enough for the local farmers to use it comfortably. The trained model is accurate enough to predict most of the images, accurately.

The project has future improvements as well. As the trained model is capable enough to classify the leaf image in 4 categories. The model can further be trained for more diseases by increasing the input dataset and training it. The implemented website is in Hindi language only. It can be made multi language by using Google APIs.

VI. REFERENCES

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